

D6.3 Möbius Closing Event

Project ref. no.	957185
Project title	Möbius: The power of prosumers in publishing
Project duration	1 st March 2021 – 30 th of March 2024 (36 months)
Website	www.mobius-project.eu
Related WP/Task	WP6 / T6.1
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Document due date	29/02/2024 (M36)
Actual delivery date	29/02/2024 (M36)
Deliverable leader	FMWC
Document status	Final

Revision History

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
0.1		FMWC	Initial draft version Clara Pont
0.2	12.02.2024	MVB	1 st review
0.3	13.02.2024	EUT	2 nd review

Executive Summary

This deliverable aims to provide the details of the final event organised for the public dissemination of the project outcomes and findings carried out by the Consortium (T6.1). Since the Möbius consortium is multidisciplinary, gathering industrial, artistic, social sciences and technological expertise, it was set that it would showcase its results in two of the largest cultural and technological events in Europe, Möbius Closing Event, explicitly focusing on the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023 (by MVB) and the Mobile World Congress Barcelona 2024 (by MWCcapital).

The Frankfurt Book Fair is the most important international trade fair for publishing and content. Experts from global publishing meet partners from the technology industry and related creative industries such as film and games. Meanwhile, the Mobile World Congress Barcelona is the largest and most influential event for the connectivity ecosystem for global mobile operators, device manufacturers, technology providers, vendors, content owners, or professionals interested in the future of tech. Intense dissemination activities and rigorous impact assessment has been organised to maximise the impact of the results on the publishing industry and the European media ecosystem as a whole.

The primary objective of this report is to provide a comprehensive assessment of the events' outcomes and communication strategies employed. The report contextualises both events and offers detailed information about the two event communication plans created and executed before, during and after the events. It emphasises the significance of the project's activities, such as panels, workshops, piloting activities and booths, in conveying the project's message and engaging the audience effectively, detailing which tools and channels were used.

Table of Contents

REVISION HISTORY	2
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	2
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	3
LIST OF FIGURES.....	4
LIST OF TABLES	5
TERMINOLOGY AND ACRONYMS.....	6
1. INTRODUCTION.....	7
1.1.1 <i>Objectives of the deliverable</i>	7
2. EVENT CONTEXT AND OBJECTIVES	9
2.1 FRANKFURT BOOK FAIR 2023.....	10
2.2 MOBILE WORLD CONGRESS 2024.....	11
2.3 OBJECTIVES.....	11
3. EVENT ACTIVITIES	12
3.1 ACTIVITIES AT FRANKFURT BOOK FAIR 2023	12
3.2 ACTIVITIES AT MOBILE WORLD CONGRESS 2024	16
4. EVENT COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLAN: MÖBIUS CLOSING EVENT AT THE FRANKFURT BOOK FAIR 2023	16
4.1 BEFORE THE EVENT.....	17
4.2 DURING	24
4.3 POST.....	31
5. EVENT COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLAN: MÖBIUS CLOSING EVENT AT THE MOBILE WORLD CONGRESS 2024	33
5.1 BEFORE THE EVENT.....	33
5.2 DURING THE EVENT	37
5.3 AFTER THE EVENT	38
6. PARTNERS AND ECOSYSTEM.....	38
6.1 FRANKFURT BOOK FAIR 2023.....	38
6.2. MOBILE WORLD CONGRESS 2024	39
7. CONCLUSIONS.....	39

List of Figures

Figure 1: Map of the stakeholders	10
Figure 2: Images of the Preliminary results presentation at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023	14
Figure 3: Images of the Policy event at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023.....	15
Figure 4: Image of the Workshop at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023.....	15
Figure 5: Post on the website with information about the Closing Event at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023.....	17
Figure 6: LinkedIn posts	18
Figure 7: X posts	19
Figure 8: Save the date newsletters	20
Figure 9: #MeetMöbiusSpeaker posts	21
Figure 10: Video banners in X and LinkedIn.....	22
Figure 11: Report of the LinkedIn paid campaign results.....	22
Figure 12: Buchmesse's APP and Scrab.in	23
Figure 13: MVB's Mailing report	24
Figure 14: X posts during the event.....	25
Figure 15: LinkedIn posts during the event.....	25
Figure 16: Some of the Möbius partners' posts during the event	26
Figure 17: Posts from HaDEA and MediaVerse talking about the Möbius Project.....	26
Figure 18: Images of the Möbius booth	27
Figure 19: Möbius flyers	29
Figure 20: Image of the flyers in a Möbius stand	29
Figure 21: Images of the The Möbius Book Experiences.....	30
Figure 22: Main media covering the Möbius press release	31
Figure 23: Posts in X and LinkedIn with the Frankfurt Book Fair press release link	32
Figure 24: LinkedIn post with the Möbius recap video at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023	33
Figure 25: Save the date Möbius at the Mobile World Congress 2024.....	34
Figure 26: Save the date Möbius at the Mobile World Congress 2024 in the December newsletter.....	35
Figure 27: Möbius detailed activities at the Mobile World Congress 2024.....	36
Figure 28: Tweets of the #MeetOurSpeakers campaign	37

Figure 29: Render of the MWCB stand at Mobile World Congress 202437
Figure 30: Some of the members of the Möbius project at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023.....39

List of Tables

Table 1: List of the identified stakeholders..... 9

Terminology and Acronyms

<i>EC</i>	<i>European Commission</i>
<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>EUT</i>	<i>Eurecat</i>
<i>FEP</i>	<i>Federation of European Publishers</i>
<i>FMWC</i>	<i>Mobile World Capital Barcelona</i>
<i>FP</i>	<i>Framework Programme</i>
<i>KKW</i>	<i>Kunstkraftwerk Leipzig</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>

1. Introduction

The Möbius Closing Event is the final event for publicly disseminating the project outcomes and findings. Its objectives are to allow the project partners to explain the Möbius preliminary outcomes, ensure cross-sectorial and cross-disciplinarity, showcase the Möbius Experimental Productions, and final test the Möbius Applications.

The Möbius Closing Event was celebrated on two dates following the calendar of two of the most relevant events for the Möbius' ecosystem and stakeholders: Frankfurt Book Fair 2023 (18-22 October) and Mobile World Congress 2024 (26-29 February). The overall of the Möbius final event is attached to Task 6.1. Dissemination and Communication for public dissemination of project outcomes and findings. Thus, target key actors of the publishing sector and prosumers, with MVB taking the lead for Frankfurter Buchmesse, as a subsidiary company of the German Association of Publishers and Booksellers, and Mobile World Capital Barcelona for MWC24, being the host of MWC and 4YFN in Barcelona.

As the Möbius consortium is multidisciplinary, considering different types of expertise such as industrial, artistic, social and technological, the results were showcased in two of the most significant cultural and technological events in Europe, in which the partners MVB and FMWC are directly involved in their organisation, respectively.

The main activities showcasing the Möbius project's preliminary results and outcomes occurred during the Frankfurt Book Fair. In order to cover the last period of the project findings, the second part of the Möbius Closing Event has been scheduled to happen at the Mobile World Congress Barcelona 2024.

2. Objectives of the deliverable

This deliverable is providing the description of the project activities with a particular focus on the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023 and the Mobile World Congress Barcelona 2024. The primary aim is to provide a comprehensive report on the outcomes of the Möbius Closing Event, where the project officially showcased its achieved results.

This report will offer a clear and detailed understanding of the following key aspects:

- **Objective Attainment:** How the project successfully met its objectives during the Möbius Closing Event is to be assessed in this report.
- **Impact on Targeted Groups:** The impact and reception of the project within the specific target groups is to be analysed.
- **Utilised Tools and Channels:** The tools and channels to disseminate information, engage with stakeholders, and promote the Möbius Closing Event is to be outlined.
- **Activities Undertaken:** An overview of the various activities celebrated within the frame of the Möbius Closing Event is to be provided.

Various sources were used to communicate and disseminate the Möbius Closing Event, including the project's website, newsletters, social media, press releases, videos and presence at the stand. The following report aims to include its impact.

Thus, a comprehensive and insightful report is presented highlighting the achievements, impacts, and communication strategies employed during the Möbius Closing Event at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023 and the Mobile World Congress Barcelona 2024.

3. Event Context and Objectives

One of the main activities of the Möbius project was the Möbius Closing Event, considered one of the main activities within the communication and dissemination work package. Two key moments have helped to celebrate the final ceremony: Frankfurt Book Fair 2023 (18-22 October) and Mobile World Congress 2024 (26-29 February).

Frankfurt Book Fair 2023 is one of the most influential fairs in the publishing sector. It is where the book trends are decided, where publishers discuss strategy, content, new format, etc. While the Mobile World Congress is the most influential fair in new technology. Both gather all stakeholders represented in the project (see the table below):

Stakeholder	Benefits from Möbius
Prosumer Sector	Recognition of the prosumer value within the publishing sector.
Policy and Society	<p>Policy aspects related to creating change towards a more conducive ecosystem for publishing industries, through research and innovation programmes.</p> <p>Policy recommendations for steering a case for fair and sustainable cooperation with prosumer communities.</p>
Publishing Sector	By adopting the Möbius solutions, the publishing sector will have the possibility to access new markets and reach new public but also apply new business models that will encourage collaboration between artists, researchers, users, technology SMEs.
Media Industry	Commercialisation of the results and access to replicable business models.
ICT Sector	Creation of immersive book using 3D audio and VR.
Research, Academia and Open-Source Communities	Reinforce research activities and open-source communities in the field of the publishing sector and the prosumers. The project will contribute to make progress in the state of art regarding user research by endowing unprecedented reach and scale capabilities to living lab approaches.
General Public	The public will benefit of the new immersive experiences. Möbius will bring a new way of consuming books.

Table 1: List of the identified stakeholders

Figure 1: Map of the stakeholders

4. Frankfurt Book Fair 2023

The Frankfurt Book Fair is the most important international trade fair for publishing and content. Experts from global publishing meet partners from the technology industry and related creative industries such as film and games. It took place from the 18th to the 22nd of October 2023, five months before the end of the project (March 2024). This was its 75th edition, which received 105,000 trade visitors, 4,000 companies from 130 different countries, 110,000 general public, and 7,000 media representatives, according to the Frankfurter Buchmesse. Thus, it is the hub of the international rights and licensing trade and the starting point for new cooperations and business models.

That is why for reaching stakeholders in the publishing industries, and by extension policy stakeholders with a say in the book sector (e.g., copyright, geo-blocking, pricing, taxing, ISBN, etc.), Möbius leveraged mainly on MVB and FEP own networks and activities. MVB, the main service provider and technology consultant for book marketing in the German publishing market and a subsidiary company of the German Association of Publishers and Booksellers, is linked to the organisation of Frankfurt Book Fair. This is the reason why the Möbius consortium has decided to celebrate its closing event at the German fair, to reach publishers, prosumers, the creative and cultural industries, policy and society, and academia, researchers and open-source communities. MVB was responsible for the organisation of the booth and the placement of the Mobile Immersive Book Box within the ARTs+ Areal; the booking of rooms for workshops and panel discussions, as well as the effective collaboration with the project

Aldus UP to present the Möbius pre-results round table on its stage. The German company also sent numerous invitations to their customers and registered publishers to advertise the Möbius activities and workshops planned during the Book Fair and engage them in participating.

5. Mobile World Congress 2024

Since the Mobile World Congress 2024 is celebrated in Barcelona (Spain) and takes place from the 26th to the 29th of February, exactly at the end of the project, the Möbius consortium decided to present and showcase the final results of Möbius during this event.

Mobile World Congress Barcelona is the largest and most influential event for the connectivity ecosystem for global mobile operators, device manufacturers, technology providers, vendors, content owners, or professionals interested in the future of tech.

Tens of thousands of senior executives from the top global companies, international governments and tech businesses converge at MWC Barcelona to make decisions. This means that many of the relevant stakeholders for the Möbius ecosystem will gather in the Spanish city those days: technology sector, policy and society, media industry, publishers, prosumers, creative and cultural industries, the general public, etc.

The Möbius final results presentation has been organised in this context, which it will be a panel discussion with experts to dynamize the session.

6. Objectives

The objectives of the Möbius Closing Event are the following ones:

1. **To explain the Möbius preliminary/final results:** Provide a clear and understandable presentation of the preliminary and final outcomes and findings of the Möbius project. It aims to communicate the project's results to relevant stakeholders, such as the supportive initiatives, the targeted audience, or the general public.
2. **To ensure cross-sectoriality and cross-disciplinarity:** It involves fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange across different sectors and disciplines. It seeks to promote a holistic approach to innovation within the publishing sector.
3. **To showcase the Möbius Experimental Productions:** It focuses on highlighting and presenting Möbius experiences (Mobile Immersive Book Box, VR headsets adaptation) created by the Möbius project. It may involve exhibitions, demonstrations, or other means to display them.
4. **To final test the Möbius Applications:** It refers to the comprehensive testing and validation of the applications developed as part of the Möbius project. It ensures that the Möbius Applications (Möbius Book Creator and Player, ad Prosumers Intelligence Toolkit) are thoroughly assessed and refined, aiming for quality assurance and functionality.

7. Event activities

In the subsequent sections, the strategies for effectively managing the events and activities during the Möbius Closing Event, aligning them with the outlined objectives, will be elaborated upon. As brainstormed and meticulously planned, each aspect of the project's presence at the Frankfurt Book Fair and Mobile World Congress became evident: organising panel discussions and roundtable sessions would be the most effective means of disseminating the results and fostering cross-sectoral collaboration and interdisciplinary engagement. This approach allowed the project to seamlessly and naturally address all critical points while engaging in meaningful conversations with Möbius partners and actively interacting with the target audience. Apart from that, the Möbius presence in each fair with a branded stand to communicate the project's activity to the visitors is a key point to maximise the impact.

8. Activities at Frankfurt Book Fair 2023

The Möbius Project was present at Hall 4.1, H25 and H33 with a **Möbius Booth and Möbius Mobile Immersive Book Box** during the four days (18th to 22nd of October) of the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023. Organised by MVB in cooperation with Mobile World Capital Barcelona and Kunstkraftwerk Leipzig, the visitors could discover the project and enjoy the immersive experience provided by the Mobile Immersive Book Box and its adaptation into virtual reality with VR headsets. People's feedback was collected through these ongoing activities.

The Möbius Book Experiences

These experiences aim at demonstrating and validating the project value proposition through user-driven and enriched book experiences based on *The influence of blue*, the Italian novel by Giulio Ravizza, published by Bookabook in 2019, and *Fantasy into Möbius*, the short story by Filippo Rubulotta which won the project's Call for manuscripts in 2022. The Möbius experimental productions consist of four elements: . The Möbius experimental productions consist of four elements:

- The immersive individual book experiences generated using the **Möbius Book Creator** and accessible through the **Möbius Book Player**.
- The VR experience is a 360 virtual-reality visualisation of the fantasy world of the Möbius novels.
- The **Möbius immersive book art installation** (an immersive show created by Franz Fischnaller, Media Artist, and Rupert Huber, Sound Designer, produced by Kunstkraftwerk Leipzig). The immersive art installation is accompanied by its soundtrack, specially composed to enhance the storytelling experience.

- The **Mobile Immersive Book Box**: is a transportable 5m x 5m x 3m projection space with a 3D audio system, allowing an immersive experience of the contents played in the Möbius immersive book art installation.

Preliminary results presentation: “How to effectively move to a digital transition within a publishing house”

Furthermore, other activities will be organised throughout the event to disseminate and present the project's preliminary outcomes and results and generate fruitful discussions with industry experts. Thus, within these activities, on the very first day of the fair (18/10/2023), a presentation of preliminary project results at the Aldus Up Stage (ARTS+ Areal, Hall 4.1) was organised under the title “How to effectively move to a digital transition within a publishing house”. It was divided into two parts, all moderated by the project coordinator from Eurecat, Rosa Maria Araujo. Firstly, the project was briefly introduced to the audience by the moderator. Then, it started the turn to explain how the Möbius Book was created and evolved to the different Möbius Experimental Productions (Mobile Immersive Book Box, VR headsets, Möbius Book Art Installation). Bookabook and KKW developed these explanations, and the Media Artist Franz Fischnaller, showed the process and the images he created for the experiences of the books. The author of the chosen book *The Influence of Blue* for the Möbius Book, Giulio Ravizza, was invited to give his acquaintance as he could see his literary work complemented with such immersive experiences.

This roundtable swapped, and another group of partners climbed to the stage. Still under Eurecat's moderation, DEN Institute, IMEC and IN2 explained the Möbius Book (Player and Creator) and the Prosumers Intelligence Toolkit while highlighting the importance of having tested these applications with their target users and received their feedback to improve it. During this roundtable, the importance of books and reading was discussed, and how the digital transformation of the book sector creates the opportunity for younger generations to connect through reading, establish close connections with the community, and give further facilities to those with disabilities was discussed. Thirty people joined, and a Q&A opened when it ended, which raised interesting topics and fruitful conversations regarding the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in the process of digitalising publishing houses and immersive book experiences, but also how would the future of the sector be in terms of technology improvements.

Figure 2: Images of the Preliminary results presentation at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023

Policy Event: How cross-sectoriality shapes the publishing industry by comparing theories, practices, and data to inform future strategies.

The second activity in the frame of the 75th Frankfurter Buchmesse and the Möbius Closing event was the Get-together and the Policy Event organised by DEN Institute with the support of Mobile World Capital Barcelona and MVB. The event focused on how cross-sectoriality shapes the publishing industry by comparing theories, practices, and data to inform future strategies.

The discussion was composed of five panellists and was moderated by Stella Diakou, Researcher at DEN Institute. On stage, Miha Kovač, Professor (University of Ljubljana) and author, guest of honour of the Buchmesse 2023; José Manuel Anta, Director of FANDE (Federation of National Associations of Book Distributors) and IPDA (International Publishing Distribution Association); Simone Lippold, expert and manager, HelloAgile; Arantza Larrauri, General Director and Advisor of Librandia / Market Director of Europe and LATAM at Grupo De Marque; Federico Pianzola, Assistant Professor in Computational Humanities, University of Groningen. Twenty-one people attended between the get-together and the policy event part.

The first round of questions aimed to set the scene by tapping into the speakers' experience concerning the state of the publishing and book sector. The speakers discussed the importance of book reading in its traditional form as an essential practice that enhances mental and emotional development and critical thinking, as well as the advantages of digital social reading. This was also an opportunity to hear about PARIX, the school for the Spanish book that aims to re-skill and upskill professionals and to discuss the role of technology in the transformations that are taking place in the sector. In addition, the role of technology in improving and facilitating the missions of public institutions such as libraries was explored.

The second round of questions aimed at bridging the speakers' expertise with the Möbius project's goals to highlight the role of prosumers and cross-sectoriality. The speakers discussed the role of data in informing the publishing industry and the importance of a forward-thinking mindset to form successful cross-sectoral collaborations. Finally, through a comparison between the European and the LATAM market, the role of the European Union and especially of the Commission in fostering research, innovation and cross-sectoral collaborations in the book and publishing sector was highlighted. The policy event was a great opportunity to discuss some of the industry's main issues and explore ways of moving forward while taking advantage of the technological advancements that are revolutionising the book and book publishing sector.

Figure 3: Images of the Policy event at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023

Workshop: Let's test the Prosumers Intelligence Toolkit

The third and last activity was on Friday (20th of October 2023, from 11:00 to 12:00), organised by IMEC, DEN Institute, IN2, MVB and Mobile World Capital Barcelona to test the **Prosumers Intelligence Toolkit (PIT)** in a workshop format. It was planned to start with a brief introduction on behalf of IMEC about the platform and then divide the attendees into groups so they could answer the questions asked by adding post-its in posters and sharing opinions. Despite promoting the workshop via different channels, several other activities were happening simultaneously, and very few people participated. Despite the numerous publishers invited by MVB, the number of attendees was insufficient to proceed with the workshop (find the communication and dissemination plan for the different Möbius activities scheduled at the book fair in Chapter 4).

Figure 4: Image of the Workshop at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023

9. Activities at Mobile World Congress 2024

Mobile World Congress Barcelona 2024 is taking place between the 26th and the 29th of February, at the time of writing the current deliverable. The Möbius Project is at Hall 8.1 (stand number 8.1B55). The stand is located inside Mobile World Capital Barcelona's one in the 4YFN area to leverage this Möbius partner's visibility inside this so-called technological event. Visitors are being able to discover more information about the project and enjoy the immersive experience of adapting the Mobile Immersive Book Box to the VR headsets. Moreover, Möbius is showcasing its innovative applications: the Möbius Book Player, the Möbius Book Creator and the Prosumers Intelligence Toolkit. These are still ongoing activities that Möbius Consortium is performing during the congress to communicate and disseminate the project and showcase the immersive experience and Möbius applications, in order to receive attendant's feedback.

On the second day of the Mobile World Congress / 4YFN 2024, Möbius has organised a round table where industry leaders and experts have gathered to highlight the innovative technologies developed by the project. Starting with Julià Vicens, Head of Computational Social Science at Eurecat, who has introduced the project's main features. Richard Elelman, Head of Politics at EURECAT in Barcelona and co-leader of the RENAISSANCE Science-Art-Sustainability programme, has emphasized the European Commission's role in creative and cultural industries. Alenxandru Stan, Innovation Project Manager at IN2 Digital Innovations, has given insights on using digital and data-driven technologies in the cultural sector, exploring the potentialities of prosumer communities and AI. Followed by Enrico Turrin, Deputy Director at the Federation of European Publishers, who has gone through the latest trends in the publishing industry, shedding light on topics such as audiobooks, social media's impact and immersiveness. Lastly, Markus Loëffler, Founder of the Kunstkraftwerk Leipzig, has shared some benefits of integrating Möbius technologies into publishing.

10. Event Communication and Dissemination Plan: Möbius Closing Event at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023

The Communication and Dissemination plan for the Frankfurt Book Fair started a month and a half before the event, marking the culmination of meticulous preparations that began in February 2023 on behalf of MVB in collaboration with Mobile World Capital Barcelona. These preparations encompassed a range of activities, including booth reservation, stand graphics design, pre-arrangements for the set-up of the art installation with all its technical requirements, agenda creation, room and stage bookings for panel discussions and roundtables, and the identification of speakers to participate in these events. A communication campaign was initiated with all elements in place and a well-defined strategy to promote the Möbius Closing Event. The consortium received a communication toolkit to ensure widespread dissemination, empowering them to spread the word through their respective networks.

11. Before the event

The strategy followed to communicate and disseminate the Möbius project was to create awareness, to engage, and to boost.

1. Awareness:

First, a blog post was posted on the Möbius website explaining the different activities that were about to take place in the frame of the book fair on behalf of the Möbius project. The aim behind the publication of this piece of news was to use this link for the promotion of the several panel discussions, workshops and presence at the booth and Mobile Immersive Book Box on the Möbius social media channels and one-on-one messages to the partners' networks.

Figure 5: Post on the website with information about the Closing Event at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023

Therefore, a post for each of the Möbius initiatives in the fair was published as a save the date, about to disclaim more information soon on its social media channels, LinkedIn and X (Twitter), not on Instagram, since it is mainly used as a repository of the most relevant actions the project has put together.

Möbius
534 seguidores
1 mes

📅 Save the date in your calendar!

📍 #MöbiusProject will attend the Frankfurt Book Fair, the biggest marketplace for #publishing, with a booth at the Deutch event, and a space to showcase the Möbius Mobile Book Box!

📅 On 18-22 October 2023, in Frankfurt (Germany)
📍 At Hall 4.1, H25 and H33

Find more information here 📄 <https://ow.ly/yoLe50PENBy>
Frankfurter Buchmesse, #fmb23

Ver traducción

Möbius at Frankfurt Book Fair 2023

Come to visit our **booth** and the **Möbius Mobile Book Box!**

📅 18-22 October
📍 Hall 4.1, H25 and H33 - #fmb23

#mobiustobook mobius-project.eu

Möbius
534 seguidores
1 mes

📍 #MöbiusProject celebrates its Closing Event at *Frankfurter Buchmesse 2023* with several presentations, panels and many other activities with industry experts!

🗣️ One of them is the Möbius Policy Event and Get-together. Don't miss it!

📅 On 19 October, 10:00h-13:00h
📍 At Room Good Will, Hall 4.1

Find more information about #Möbius Closing Event activities at #fmb23 now 📄 <https://ow.ly/yoLe50PENBy>
#publishing #MöbiusBook

Ver traducción

Möbius at Frankfurt Book Fair 2023

Policy Event and Get Together

📅 19 October - 10:00h
📍 Room Good Will, Hall 4.1 - #fmb23

#mobiustobook mobius-project.eu

Möbius
534 seguidores
1 mes

📍 Will you be around *Frankfurter Buchmesse* this year?

#Möbius will present the project results to modernize the EU book #publishing industry in its Closing Event celebrated during the #fmb23 days!

📅 On 18 October, 14:00h-14:50h
📍 At Aldus Up Stage, Hall 4.1

Discover more information here 📄 <https://ow.ly/yoLe50PENBy>

Ver traducción

Möbius at Frankfurt Book Fair 2023

Möbius Closing Event: Project results presentation

📅 18 October, 14:00h
📍 Aldus Up Stage, Hall 4.1 - #fmb23

#mobiustobook mobius-project.eu

Möbius
534 seguidores
1 mes

📍 #LivingLabs can be a powerful mechanism for driving positive change in society.

The #OpenLivingLab Days of our partner *EnoLL (European Network of Living Labs)* will explore the role of human-centric innovation in shaping our lives during three days of research sessions, hands-on workshops and interactive discussions with industry experts in the following tracks: green transition, digital transition, social transition, just transition and living labs transition.

📍 The #MöbiusProject will join the event to test the Innovative Applications that consist of the #MöbiusBook, including a Player and a Creator app, and the Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit and gather feedback on the #immersivereading experience from the attendees.

📍 Barcelona
📅 21-23 September

📄 Find more information here: <https://ow.ly/FGr650PEY1v>

Co-organised by Computer Vision Center, i2CAT Foundation, Fundación Épica La Fura dels Baus, ESSI European School of Social Innovation.

#OLLD23 #LivingLabs

Ver traducción

Möbius at Open Living Labs Days

Test with us the **Möbius Player, Möbius Creator & Prosumers Intelligence Toolkit!**

📅 21-23 September
📍 Barcelona

#mobiustobook mobius-project.eu

Figure 6: LinkedIn posts

Figure 7: X posts

The first Möbius LinkedIn Newsletter was sent and also its adaptation to the Mailchimp format with this save the date of the detailed Möbius activities during the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023.

Möbius Project Newsletter
 Discover the power of prosumers in publishing and read so...
 Newsletter mensual

167 suscriptores ✓ Suscrito

Editar artículo Ver estadísticas Ver publicación

Möbius Newsletter

Modernizing the European book publishing industry

Möbius
534 seguidores

28 de septiembre de 2023

Immersive reading is the new trend in publishing

Discover the Möbius project activities at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023!

Dear Möbius Community,

The most important international trade fair for publishing and content is arriving in Frankfurt this week: yes, we are talking about the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023, in which the Möbius project is participating with several activities to celebrate its [Closing Event](#).

MORE INFO

From the 18th to the 22nd of October, experts from global publishing will meet partners from the technology industry and related creative industries such as film and games. **Möbius will be there to celebrate its Closing Event** with the following panels and workshops that you cannot miss:

1. Presentation of project results – **Wednesday 18th, 14:00h-14:50h** – Aldus Up Stage, Hall 4.1.
2. Möbius Policy Event and Get-together – **Thursday 19th, 11:00h-13:00h** – Room Good Will, Hall 4.1.
3. Möbius Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit (PIT) Workshop – **Friday 20th, 11:00h-12:00h** – Room Encounter, Hall 5.0.

Moreover, during the whole fair, Möbius will have a booth together with the **Möbius Mobile Book Box at Hall 4.1, H25 and H33**.

Click on the button below to discover more about Möbius activities and the specialists that will join our discussions!

FIND OUT MORE NOW

Hope to see you there!

Have a nice week,
The Möbius team.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 957185.

Figure 8: Save the date newsletters

2. Engagement:

This phase of the strategy started three weeks before the start of the event. It consisted of the #MeetMöbiusSpeaker campaign, to engage attendees to the policy event on “Reshaping the book and publishing sector through cross-sectoriality. Comparing and discussing theory, practices and data for a forward-looking discussion” so they could join this Möbius activity thanks to the interest of the project and for the profiles of the panellists.

Möbius
534 seguidores
2 semanas • Editado •

#MeetMöbiusSpeaker: Miha Kovač!

👤 Professor of #Publishing at the University of Ljubljana, and author and curator of the Slovenian Pavilion, guest of honor of the Frankfurter Buchmesse 2023. His main research interests are publishing and reading statistics, diversity in European book production, bestsellers in Europe and differences between print and screen reading.

Do you want to meet him? Don't miss the #MöbiusProject Policy Event and Get-Together to speak about how cross-sectoriality is shaping the book and publishing sectors and how new technologies are changing the reading experience.

📅 19 October, 11:00h-13:00h
📍 Room Good Will, Hall 4.1 - #fbm23

More information about all the #MöbiusClosingEvent activities here 📄
<https://ow.ly/yoLe50PENBy>

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Möbius
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3 semanas • Editado •

#MeetMöbiusSpeaker: José Manuel Anta!

👤 Director of FANDE (Federation of National Associations of Book Distributors) and IPDA - International Publishing Distribution Association. He is also the Coordinator of the International Event for Innovation in Books and Reading, #Readmagine, held annually in Madrid. He has published articles and interviews in Spanish and overseas publications about the distribution of cultural and leisure products.

How are new technologies reshaping the reading experience?

Meet him at #fbm23 during the #MöbiusProject Policy Event and Get-Together with several experts from the #book and #publishing industries to discover the answer to that question and to discuss how cross-sectoriality is shaping the sector.

📅 19 October, 11:00h-13:00h
📍 Room Good Will, Hall 4.1 - Frankfurter Buchmesse

Find out more about this and other #MöbiusClosingEvent activities at the fair here 📄
<https://ow.ly/yoLe50PENBy>

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Möbius
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2 semanas •

#MeetMöbiusSpeaker: Simone Lippold!

👤 Agile expert and manager at HelloAgile. She supports companies on their path of transformation from traditional structures to a modern digitized world.

You'll have the chance to meet her and discuss with her at the Möbius Policy Event during the Frankfurter Buchmesse 2023 in a panel with several experts under the title: "Reshaping the #book and #publishing sector through cross-sectoriality. Comparing and discussing theory, practices and data for a forward-looking discussion".

📅 19 October, 11:00h-13:00h
📍 Room Good Will, Hall 4.1 - #fbm23

Click here for more information about all the #MöbiusClosingEvent activities at the international fair 📄 <https://ow.ly/yoLe50PENBy>

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3 semanas • Editado •

#MeetMöbiusSpeaker: Federico Pianzola!

👤 Assistant Professor in Computational Humanities at Rijksuniversiteit Groningen. He is interested in digital social reading (how people write and read fiction online) and uses computational, qualitative, and quantitative methods to study how people read.

Listen to him at the #MöbiusProject Policy Event with a panel discussion about how cross-sectoriality is shaping the #book and #publishing sector.

📅 19 October, 11:00h-13:00h
📍 Room Good Will, Hall 4.1 - Frankfurter Buchmesse

Discover more info about the speakers of the discussion and Möbius activities at the fair here 📄 <https://ow.ly/yoLe50PENBy>

#MöbiusClosingEvent #fbm23 #H2020

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Möbius
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3 semanas • Editado •

#MeetMöbiusSpeaker: Arantza Larrauri!

General Director and Advisor of LIBRANDA (Grupo De Marque) and Market Director of Europe and Latin America at Grupo De Marque. She has been working in the book industry for over 19 years. She sees the evolution of the sector as an opportunity and great challenge.

Join her at the #MöbiusProject Policy Event "Reshaping the #book and #publishing sector through cross-sectoriality. Comparing and discussing theory, practices and data for a forward-looking discussion".

19 OCT. 11:00h-13:00h
Room Good Will, Hall 4.1 - Frankfurter Buchmesse

Discover more info about the panel discussion here <https://ow.ly/yoLe50PENBy>

#MöbiusClosingEvent #fbm23 #H2020

Ver traducción

Figure 9: #MeetMöbiusSpeaker posts

Moreover, another round of social media posts on LinkedIn and X started to further explain the panel discussions and workshop with more engaging video banners. Some of these posts with animated creativities were promoted via a paid campaign, as so was the **#MeetMöbiusSpeaker: Miha Kôvac**, since he was member of the board of guests of honours from Slovenia at the Frankfurter Buchmesse 2023 and could help to maximise the impact.

Figure 10: Video banners in X and LinkedIn

Several LinkedIn posts were boosted to promote the Frankfurt Buchmesse activities that the Möbius project was organising. See below the overall of results of the month of October 2023:

Figure 11: Report of the LinkedIn paid campaign results

3. Boost:

In the last part of the strategy to communicate the Möbius agenda for the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023, the buchmesse's application was used to network and invite targeted profiles to attend each activity. This phase started one week and a half before the fair's kick-off. Twenty-five messages per day were written during this period to publishers, digital publishers, authors, audiobook developers, eBook creators and others related to the industry, specifically to each of the scheduled panels, and to come to visit the stand and experience the Mobile Immersive Book Box.

Not only did the Frankfurter Buchmesse app's matchmaking tool work for the project but the use of Scrab.in. This is a Google extension used by Mobile World Capital Barcelona to send LinkedIn messages to targeted profiles. They sent 91 LinkedIn messages (invites) inviting professionals from the sector to attend the Möbius sessions and visit the booth.

Figure 12: Buchmesse's APP and Scrab.in

Messages were separated between sessions. MVB sent emails to 7,844 publishers to specifically invite them to the Prosumers Intelligence Toolkit Workshop, where the project's activities, tool, and objectives were explained. Nonetheless, the vast number of activities happening simultaneously and overlapping at that very time frame affected the attendance rate of the workshop.

To avoid this kind of situation, it would be recommended to consider the whole activity of the fair and its size for future editions and projects; when an event is smaller, it is

easier to attract the target audience. Also, the approach could be different, such as inviting high-level experts to do a brief presentation and their points of view about the workshop so that they might attract bigger audiences.

Figure 13: MVB's Mailing report

12. During

Throughout Möbius' participation in the Frankfurt Book Fair, Mobile World Capital Barcelona maintained ongoing communication, actively promoting Möbius's scheduled activities and summarising its accomplishments.

X:

Figure 14: X posts during the event

LinkedIn:

Möbius
548 seguidores
2 semanas · 🌐

📅 It's been the first day of Möbius at the **Frankfurter Buchmesse**, the ultimate hub for #publishing innovation!

We have presented a panel on behalf of the Möbius partners aiming to share the project results we have until now under the title "How to effectively move to a digital transformation within a publishing house" at the Aldus Up Stage, which had 30 attendees!

📱 We also showcase the Möbius Mobile Book Box and our Möbius Applications. Don't miss them and dive into immersive book experiences!

🇩🇪 Join us from October 18-22, 2023, in Frankfurt at Hall 4.1, H25, and H33.

Details here 📄 <https://mobius-project.eu/>

#fsm23 #MöbiusBookBox 📖📱

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Möbius
548 seguidores
2 semanas · 🌐

📅 DAY 2 recap!

The #MöbiusProject Closing Event is in full swing at **Frankfurter Buchmesse 2023**, featuring captivating presentations, engaging panels, and insightful discussions with industry experts!

📖 This morning, we were immersed in the Möbius Policy Event and Get together focused on "Reshaping the book and publishing sector through cross-sectoriality. Comparing and discussing theory."

It was a very insightful panel where we listened to inspirational thoughts, **José Manuel Anta**, Director of IPDA - International Publishing Distribution Association, focused on the need for the upskilling and reskilling of the professionals of the publishing sector in terms of using the newest tools in the market: "The industry is creating excellent tools, but at the same time, we need people to know how to use them. Technology is transforming the skills of professionals in the sector. That is why it is essential to upskill and reskill professionals."

📅 Join us tomorrow at our workshop on the Consumers Intelligence Toolkit at 11:00, Hall 5, Room Encounter, GATE 5! You'll see the Möbius signs!

#fsm23 #MöbiusBook #Publishing

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Möbius
548 seguidores
2 semanas · 🌐

📅 DAY 3 Recap!

Möbius Experimental Productions are getting much attention today with the opening of the **Frankfurter Buchmesse** to the public! 📖 Come to our booth in Hall 4.1, H25 and H33 and experience the Mobile Immersive Book Box and its VR headsets adaptation!

We are sharing 📖 "The Influence of Blue", an enriched book experience based on **Giulio Ravizza's** novel, published by **bookabook** in 2019 and 📖 "Fantasy into Möbius", inspired by **Filippo Rubolotta's** award-winning short story from our 2022 Call for Manuscripts.

Stay tuned for more information!
<https://mobius-project.eu/>

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Marta Portalés Oliva, Ph.D. y 9 personas más
1 vez compartido

Figure 15: LinkedIn posts during the event

The Möbius partners also posted about the Möbius participation in the Frankfurter Book Fair:

Figure 16: Some of the Möbius partners' posts during the event

Also, the project received social media support from its ecosystem:

Figure 17: Posts from HaDEA and MediaVerse talking about the Möbius Project

At the booth, visitors were given several flyers that the Möbius communication team (FMWC) designed to inform about the Möbius Agenda at the Frankfurt Book Fair, the explanation of the

Möbius Book Experiences, and the description of the inspirational stories to develop the Mobile Immersive Book Box and its adaptation into VR headsets.

The booth:

Figure 18: Images of the Möbius booth

The flyers:

About the Möbius Book Experiences

The Möbius Book Experiences refer to the immersive digital art show experience designed and developed by Franz Fischler for the Möbius consortium based on the fantasy novel by Giulio Ravizza "The Influence of Blue" (Book 1) and "Fantasy into Möbius" (Book 2) written by Filippo Rubiotta. The experiences include audio/visual exhibits, mobile installations, and 360 VR visualizations.

More info:

Möbius

Möbius Book Experience

Mobile Immersive Book Box & VR Möbius Experience

Mobile Immersive Book Box (MIBB)

Is a portable immersive digital art installation that is intended to provide a unique and engaging way for audiences to experience the fantasy world of the Möbius novels. It is adapted for the short audio/visual versions of the books and can be used for itinerant exhibits.

VR Möbius Experience

A 360-degree virtual reality visualization of the fantasy world of the Möbius novels. It includes a short audio/visual version of the books rendered in 360 VR. The VR experience is designed to be displayed in a Head-Mounted Display (HMD).

Book 1 The Influence of Blue

A fantasy story that deals with a world vision where the influence of the colour blue has to be eliminated to create a pacific living without passion and responsibilities. A society where humans are immersed into a hedonistic, decadent boring and flat state, where a general amnesia dominates over them and global knowledge is managed through "Intelligit", a social networked-AI system.

Book 2 Fantasy into Möbius

In this story, a spaceship navigates a cybernetic tunnel and leads us to a laboratory filled with guarded cryogenic capsules. From these, Jack and Conrad emerge, encountering each other past cryo-sleep. Guided by a mysterious figure, they are soon presented with a captivating view of earth, highlighting a scenic mountain landscape.

Möbius Closing Event Agenda Möbius at the Frankfurt Book Fair

18th October
14:00 - 14:50 (Aldus Up Stage, 41 G19)
How to effectively move to a digital transformation within a publishing house

19th October
11:00 - 12:00 | Room Good Will (Hall 4.1)
Get-together + Catering
12:00 - 13:00 | **Reshaping the book and publishing sector through cross-sectoriality. Comparing and discussing theory**

20th October
11:00 - 12:00 | Room Encounter Hall 5.0
Let's test the Möbius Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit!

21st October
All day long
Come to booth H25 and H33 (Hall 4.1) and enjoy our applications and immersive experiences!

22nd October
Don't stop the party!
We will still be at both H25 and H33 (Hall 4.1), let's have a collective reading experience!

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 95785.

Möbius The power of prosumers in publishing

Möbius is an initiative funded under the European Commission Horizon 2020 programme that aims to modernize the European book publishing industry by remodeling the traditional value chains and business models uncovering the prosumers potential and delivering new enriched media experiences.

Möbius book experience

An immersive and interactive book experience through the Möbius Player, using binocular reproduction, individuals will be able to use the Möbius App for immersive reading and to enjoy the social interaction features.

Möbius book art installation

A fixed immersive installation including experiences of about 15 minutes each will be produced by experienced immersive artists trained at the Quintana Innova! School and in the visualization of stories.

#mobiusbook mobius-project.eu

Immersive book box

Möbius will design and construct a projection space, to be explored by 4-5 people at a time. The walls will be transparent tissue screens, allowing projections to shine through from the outside, and a 3D audio installation will be adapted for allowing a truly immersive experience.

Möbius book VR experience

The Möbius book box will be adapted to VR-headsets, to provide a convenient user-experience without the need for any installation, being made available via social media for easy download to own VRs.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 95785.

#mobiusbook mobius-project.eu

THE MÖBIUS' INNOVATIVE APPLICATIONS

The **Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit** was developed to aid publishers in their hunt for market insights and digital data on reader communities.

The **Möbius Book** allows writers (Möbius Book Creator) and readers (Möbius Book Player) to create and consume immersive and engaging reading experiences by combining textual, auditive and visual content.

Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit

For publishers. You can now increase your insights via our comprehensive dashboard. Test it here to how to gather and present data from online communities.

Möbius Book Creator

For authors. It supports (aspiring) writers in building stories enhanced with audiovisual content and 3D-audio. Test this web-based application to transform your stories into immersive experiences!

Möbius Book Player

For readers. To immerse yourself in stories through text, 3D-audio, and visual content. Try our mobile application for readers!

mobius_europe Möbius mobius_europe

THE TESTING PROCEDURE IN 3 STEPS

- 1 Try The Appl!**
Test the Möbius applications on your own device or come visit us at the booth to see what it's all about.
- 2 Tell Us What You Think!**
The app has a built-in survey and you can come talk to us at the booth! We are curious to know what you think and will gladly note your feedback.
- 3 Improve the Experience!**
Your input is analysed by our researchers and the app will be improved for our next piloting events.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 95785.

Figure 19: Möbius flyers

Figure 20: Image of the flyers in a Möbius stand

The Möbius Book Experiences:

Figure 21: Images of the The Möbius Book Experiences

During the project's participation in the Frankfurt Book Fair, which was a key component of the Möbius closing event featuring a variety of prepared activities, as well as the presence of consortium at the event's booth, FMWC actively disseminated the project's outputs and preliminary results to the visiting attendees.

Not only social media coverage was fulfilled, but also FMWC engaged an audiovisual production company based in Frankfurt, Silent Village, to document the most significant moments of Möbius' activities at the Frankfurt Book Fair. They crafted a thorough recap video that effectively conveyed the project's essence through visuals, including highlights from panel discussions, debates, productions, and quotes from various Möbius partners.

Furthermore, FMWC wrote a press release that provided an overview of the project's actions during the Buchmesse. This release incorporated quotes from panel discussions and roundtable sessions, and it underwent validation by all consortium members. On the 20th of October, 2023, Mobile World Capital Barcelona distributed this press release using the

Einpresswire platform. The distribution garnered substantial media attention, with a total of 214 impacts. Notable media outlets that covered the press release included [AP News](#), German Science & Technology Today, Spain Technology News Network, The German Update, and The German News Today.

Media Reprints:

Here is a list of independent news publishers where we can track the publication of your press release. Publishers are not required to report back to us. You could very well appear on others.

Click on the logos to view the reprints.

Figure 22: Main media covering the Möbius press release

13. Post

After the conclusion of the Frankfurt Book Fair, FMWC shared a concise summary of the project's activities across its social media platforms. [FMWC also provided a direct link to the updated Möbius website, where visitors could access the detailed press release.](#) This allowed to inform the project's audience about the insightful topics covered in the panel and roundtable discussions.

Figure 23: Posts in X and LinkedIn with the Frankfurt Book Fair press release link

Upon receiving the recap video, FMWC launched a campaign to promote it and encapsulate the Möbius' activities at the Frankfurt Book Fair and its accomplishments up to that point. This campaign served as a teaser of what the project has done to its target audience, hinting that those attending Mobile World Congress 2024 in Barcelona would have the opportunity to get to know the project's conclusive results.

The LinkedIn post to promote the Möbius recap video was also promoted through a paid campaign.

📺 Look back at the magic of Möbius at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023! Our comprehensive recap video captures the essence of our journey—energy, innovation, and collaboration. Explore the Möbius project's incredible moments at the world's largest book fair. Watch now:

<https://lnkd.in/dAwkJH3C>

#mobiusbook #mobiusproject

Figure 24: LinkedIn post with the Möbius recap video at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023

14. Event Communication and Dissemination Plan: Möbius Closing Event at the Mobile World Congress 2024

The Communication and Dissemination plan for the Mobile World Congress 2024 in Barcelona started a month and a half before the event. The preparation for Möbius's participation in this event began weeks before the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023. Includes the booth reservation within the Mobile World Capital Barcelona's stand, stage booking for a panel discussion and results presentation. Thus, a communication campaign was created with all elements in place and a well-defined strategy to promote the Möbius Closing Event. It followed the same structure and organisation as the one for the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023. To ensure widespread dissemination, FMWC equipped the entire consortium with a communication toolkit, empowering them to spread the word through their network.

15. Before the event

Since the communication and dissemination strategy for Möbius participation in the Mobile World Congress 2023 followed the same strategy as the one used for the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023, it started a month and a half before the event by making awareness, engaging and boosting the messages to the targeted audience.

Figure 25: Save the date Möbius at the Mobile World Congress 2024

First, a save-the-date message was released to the Möbius social media channels for the 27th of February at 12:00 CET in the 4YFN zone for a one-hour round table discussion of the future of creative and cultural industries and the potential of the Möbius technologies.

Moreover, the information about the save the date was included in the Möbius LinkedIn Newsletter for the month of December 2023.

December Digest: Möbius Monthly Highlights

Möbius
001 seguidores

29 de diciembre de 2023

[Abrir lector interactivo](#)

Dear Möbius Community,

We are delighted to share the latest updates and achievements from the Möbius project. As we approach the culmination of the project in March 2024, we invite you to look back with us and celebrate the strides we've made in modernising the European book publishing industry.

Exclusive Interviews from Frankfurt Book Fair 2023

Immerse yourself in the essence of literary innovation with Möbius! Watch a captivating series of insightful short interviews conducted during the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023. Gain deeper insights into our collective efforts and contributions with interviews featuring Möbius consortium partners: Miha Kovac, Anabel Acuña, Markus Löffler, and Alexandru Stan.

- Watch the interviews here: <https://mobius-project.eu/frankfurt-flashback-its-a-wrap/>

Save the Date! Möbius Project Culmination at MWC24

On February 27th, 2024, join us at MWC24 in Barcelona for a one-hour round table discussion on the future of creative and cultural industries and the potential of Möbius project's technologies. The event will take place at 12:00 CET in the 4YFN zone, followed by networking with industry leaders from 13:00-13:30 CET. Experience a demonstration of Möbius MPIT, Creator, Player, and VR Headsets. Stay tuned for more details.

Figure 26: Save the date Möbius at the Mobile World Congress 2024 in the December newsletter

As more information about the activities was being released, new communications were published:

 Möbius · Siguiendo
Servicios y consultoría de TI

📅 Experience the future of storytelling with Möbius! We invite you to join us at the Mobile World Congress 2024 in Barcelona, where we will be showcasing the Möbius Book Experiences and Innovative Applications.

📍 Find us at stand 8.1B55 in the 4YFN zone from February 26th to 29th. Witness firsthand the latest advancements reshaping the landscape of the book industry.

👉 For a sneak peek into what awaits you, click here: <https://ow.ly/abxl50QxR2k>

#Möbius #MWC24

Ver traducción

Möbius at MWC24

We will be showcasing our **Möbius Book Experience** and **Innovative Applications!**

📅 26-29 February
📍 Stand 8.1B55 – 4YFN zone

#mobiusbook mobius-project.eu

Figure 27: Möbius detailed activities at the Mobile World Congress 2024

After saving the date and providing concrete information about the activities at the event, a #MeetOurSpeakers campaign was released to engage attendees at the round table on the innovative technologies developed by Möbius. This will start with Julià Vicens, Head of Computational Social Science at Eurecat, introducing the project's main features. Richard Elelman, Head of Politics at EURECAT in Barcelona and co-leader of the RENAISSANCE Science-Art-Sustainability programme, will emphasise the European Commission's role in creative and cultural industries. Alenxandru Stan, Innovation Project Manager at IN2 Digital Innovations, will give insights on using digital and data-driven technologies in the cultural sector, exploring the potentialities of prosumer communities and AI. Followed by Enrico Turrin, Deputy Director at the Federation of European Publishers, who will go through the latest trends in the publishing industry, shedding light on topics such as audiobooks, social media's impact and immersiveness. Lastly, Markus Löffler, Founder of the Kunstkraftwerk Leipzig, will share some benefits of integrating Möbius technologies into publishing. Thus, people could get interested in attending thanks to the amazing profiles of the panelists.

Möbius @mobius_europe · 29 de gen. ...

👏 Proud to introduce Prof. Dr. med. Markus Loeffler, Founder of Kunstkraftwerk & Director of the Institute of Medical Informatics, Statistics, and Epidemiology Leipzig, as a speaker at the Möbius Closing Event on Feb 27th during #MWC24.

Details: mobius-project.eu

Markus Loeffler

is a Full Professor and Director of the Institute of Medical Informatics, Statistics and Epidemiology Leipzig. He is a founder of the Kunstkraftwerk venue and has served as the Scientific Director of the LIFE Research Center for Civilization Diseases since 2008. His influential roles include membership in the Program Committee of the System Medicine Consortia (SMC), the National Steering Committee of the Medical Informatics Initiative (M-II), and the Board of Directors of the German National Cohort (GNC). Since 2018, he has been the Principal Investigator of The SMTH Consortium within the Medical Informatics Initiative.

0:04

Möbius @mobius_europe · 29 de gen. ...

🚀 Ready for inspiration? Alexandru Stan, Research and Innovation Lead at IN2 Digital Innovations, is set to enlighten us at the #Möbius Closing Event during #MWC24. Join us on Feb 27th in Barcelona to explore the world of digital creativity.

Stay tuned: mobius-project.eu

Alexandru Stan

is leading the research and innovation projects of IN2 Digital Innovations. Since 2007, he has been active in European R&D, collaborating on over 25 EU-funded projects. With a technical background in electrical and software engineering, he actively participates in the European media and creative and cultural communities. In Möbius, he led the tasks related to the development of the Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit, Möbius Creator and Möbius Player.

0:05

Möbius @mobius_europe · 23 de gen. ...

👏 Julià Vicens, Head of Computational Social Science at Eurecat, is a featured speaker at the #Möbius Closing Event during #MWC24 on Feb 27th. He is an expert in studying collective behaviour using AI and participatory methodologies.

📌 More details soon: mobius-project.eu

Julià Vicens

Julià Vicens is a research scientist specialising in the study of collective behaviour within complex systems applying a combination of computational (e.g. AI) and participatory methodologies (e.g. citizen science), where science, technology and society converge. He is leading the Computational Social Science research line at Eurecat, contributing his insights and expertise to cutting-edge research applied to gaining a comprehensive understanding of socio-technical systems.

0:07

Möbius @mobius_europe · 16 de gen. ...

👏 Happy to announce Enrico Turrin, Deputy Director and Economist at the Federation of European Publishers, as a speaker at the #Möbius Closing Event during #MWC24 on Feb 27th. Enrico is a leader in sector statistics and diverse projects.

📌 More details: mobius-project.eu

Enrico Turrin

Deputy Director and Economist, Federation of European Publishers Degree in Economics at the University Luigi Bocconi in Milan in 2000 and master's degree in International Affairs at ISPI Milan, in 2001. Project Manager at ISPI and lecturer on International Organisations from 2002. From 2005 to 2008, worked as an external expert and lecturer for ISPI and a project by the Italian Foreign Ministry. He was hired as an economist by FEP in 2008, where he is in charge of the sector statistics and of a range of other files. Deputy Director of FEP since 2012.

0:09

Figure 28: Tweets of the #MeetOurSpeakers campaign

16. During the event

The deadline for the deliverable D6.3 is the precise date when the event ends. This is why adding the communication and dissemination actions executed during the event is not possible. Nonetheless, a press release will be sent to the media through EinPressWire, and a recap social media post will be published daily.

Möbius is present at booth 8.1B55 showcasing the Möbius Book Applications, including the Möbius Book Player, the Möbius Book Creator and the Prosumers Intelligence Toolkit during the four days of the fair. We are also sharing with the visitors the Möbius VR Experience, 8 minutes and 360° VR demonstration of an enriched book experience based on *The influence of blue*, the Italian novel by Giulio Ravizza, published by Bookabook in 2019, and *Fantasy into Möbius*, the short story by Filippo Rubulotta which won the project's Call for manuscripts in 2022. The VR experience, an immersive show created by Franz Fischnaller, Media Artist, and Rupert Huber, Sound Designer, produced by Kunstkraftwerk Leipzig is being also showcased to the fair attendants.

The booth looks like the render below:

Figure 29: Render of the MWCB stand at Mobile World Congress 2024

17. After the event

After the Mobile World Congress / 4YFN 2024 ends, Möbius will share a wrap-up post on its social media channels about its participation in the event and the organised activities there. The press release will be uploaded on the project's website, where visitors will be able to access it. This will help inform the audience about the insightful topics in round table discussions. The last newsletter of the project will be sent on the 29th of February via Mailchimp and LinkedIn Newsletters. Other than that, since the project will have reached its culmination, a lessons learned blogpost will be published on the website and promoted through the project's channels.

18. Partners and Ecosystem

19. Frankfurt Book Fair 2023

The Möbius Closing Event held at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023 was a significant milestone for the project, and it brought together various internal partners to enhance Möbius' engagement within the publishing ecosystem. Seven key internal partners participated, including MVB, Mobile World Capital Barcelona, DEN Institute, IMEC, Bookabook, IN2, KKW, Eurecat, and FEP. This collaborative effort allowed the consortium to join forces and provide support during the Möbius Closing Event activities at the Frankfurt Book Fair.

The Möbius presence at the Frankfurt Book Fair, recognised as the most significant book fair globally, was a strategic move to connect with the publishing ecosystem and expand the project's reach. In addition to the policy event, where DEN Institute and FMWC featured high-level speakers from institutions and organisations such as the University of Ljubljana, Librandia, Hello Agile, University of Groningen, Federation of National Associations of Book Distributors, and the International Publishing Distribution Association, the project leveraged on this opportunity to interact with several organisations that offered potential synergies for the project.

During the Frankfurt Book Fair, the Möbius consortium could interact with organisations that have the potential to enhance the project in various ways, including testing its applications and increasing its visibility: Book2Look, The London Book Fair, Superbean.tv and the Toys Magazine. These interactions can drive the project forward through collaboration, testing opportunities, or increased visibility.

Figure 30: Some of the members of the Möbius project at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023

6.2. Mobile World Congress 2024

The upcoming Möbius Closing Event at the Mobile World Congress / 4YFN 2024 promises to be an opportunity to showcase the project's technological advancements. Anticipated attendees include key Möbius partners such as Mobile World Capital Barcelona, MVB, DEN Institute, IMEC, IN2, KKW, Eurecat, FEP, KU Leuven, and Bookabook.

The project's participation in the Mobile World Congress / 4YFN 2024 holds the potential to expand its reach, similar to the impact achieved during its previous involvement in the Frankfurt Book Fair. The Möbius consortium is eager to connect with organisations that have the potential to contribute to the project in various ways, including the chance to showcase its applications and increase its visibility.

20. Conclusions

In conclusion, the project's participation in the **Frankfurt Book Fair 2023** and **Mobile World Congress / 4YFN 2024** has been instrumental in the success of the Möbius Closing event. These sector-specific events provided valuable opportunities to engage with the project's target audience and achieve its objectives.

One of the Möbius best practices of active participation at these events as **culminating points** of the project is the importance of leveraging its existing **networks** and **partnerships**. The collaboration between **MVB** and **Mobile World Capital Barcelona**, who organised the project's participation in the Frankfurt Book Fair and Mobile World Congress, respectively,

allowed Möbius to tap into their networks and enhance the visibility of the project. This strategic approach proved highly effective in attracting attendees to the events.

A valuable **lesson learned** is the power of personalised communication. The Möbius LinkedIn page and growth hacking strategies enabled the project to **establish one-on-one connections** with its target audience, fostering meaningful engagement and encouraging them to attend the Möbius events. This approach was extended to the **event-specific mobile applications**, further enhancing Möbius' networking capabilities even though the active communication through its networks and the growth-hacking strategies deployed weren't compelling to the same extent for all the organised activities. In both events, Frankfurt and Barcelona, it had to be considered that many activities were happening simultaneously from more prominent entities.

The project's **communication and dissemination plans** were crucial in driving **engagement** and interest in the Möbius project. The increase in daily social media posts and targeted campaigns involving key experts and Möbius partners proved effective. Additionally, using **animated and video content**, including video banners, interviews, and project explanations, was essential in expanding the project's reach, mainly through **paid campaigns**. Using **newsletters** via the Mailchimp channel and LinkedIn Newsletters also contributed to the project's success in reaching the target audience. Nonetheless, the presence at the stand at each of the fairs, letting visitors know about the activities and giving them a printed agenda, has also worked very well for the project to reach the targeted audience that couldn't be reached online.

The Möbius project obtained a beneficial impact from its participation in both events throughout these communication actions, such as sending the **press releases** accordingly to its activity in each event, which generated 214 clippings for the Frankfurt Book Fair. The project's presence in a **branded** stand at each event helped to enhance its visibility to its ecosystem and grow its contacts. The consortium met new organisations to showcase the project, the applications and the experiences. Overall, **feedback** was received from 94 users for the Mobile Immersive Book Box and the VR headset experiences. (this number is only for the Buchmesse). The Möbius presence at the Frankfurter Buchmesse was an opportunity to access people who are experts in the publishing industry, as well as authors and readers. Especially during the days that the event was open to the public, it was an opportunity to access a wide range of public, from younger people to stakeholders. Overall, it was considered a good opportunity to showcase the Mobile Immersive Book Box for the first time outside Leipzig, where they were created.

The **Möbius partners** are happy about Möbius' participation in the Frankfurt Book Fair and the current Mobile World Congress in Barcelona, highlighting its dual impact strategy after circulating a **survey** among the project's partners concerning the presence of the closing event in both locations. According to them, the project faced a mixed outcome in Frankfurt, with panel discussions drawing interest despite the challenge of attracting attention in a very busy event. The fair was an excellent platform for showcasing the Möbius Book and Immersive experiences to a receptive audience, although securing publishers proved challenging.

Workshops and surveys had limited impact due to low participation, primarily due to the busy schedules of publishing sector participants. Meanwhile, Möbius anticipates a two-fold impact at the Mobile World Congress in Barcelona:

“The project aims to showcase its outcomes, allowing attendees to witness tangible results. Additionally, it anticipates valuable networking opportunities and a chance to introduce Möbius to a fresh audience. The Möbius Closing Event II at Mobile World Congress Barcelona / 4YFN 2024 focuses on maximising impact through strategic dissemination and networking, prioritising engagement over piloting activities. In the booth, the team plans to engage attendees through meaningful conversations, address inquiries, and provide insightful product demonstrations.” – Anonymous partner

In summary, the project’s experience at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023 and Mobile World Congress 2024 has taught the consortium **valuable lessons** and **highlighted best practices** in communication and engagement. By capitalising on existing partnerships, personalising the project’s communication efforts, and utilising a diverse range of content and channels, we have maximised the impact of its presence at these events and achieve its goals for the Möbius project.